

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.4.5: Fire regime changes

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Description

Section 3.3.4.5 assesses the role of fire as a driver of biological invasions in Chapter 3 of IPBES assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):**

Search 1: English

Search 2: Portuguese

Search 3: Spanish

- **Search terms**

Search 1: fire review invasive OR alien OR exotic OR "non native" OR "non indigenous" "climate change"

Search 2: fogo revisão invasora OR exótica OR não-nativa "mudanças climáticas"

Search 3: fuego revisión invasora OR exótica OR "especies introducidas" "cambios climaticos"

- **Search engine:** Google Scholar

- **Date:**

Search 1: 18/9/2019

Search 2-3: 2/10/2019

-**Searched time period:**

Search 1: since 2000

Search 2: since 2000

Search 3: since 2000

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

Search 1: 30

Search 2-3: None

Selection criteria: studies covering the role of fire associated with climate change as a driver of alien species invasions, according to expert's own knowledge.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 1

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 31 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files: [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)